

Analysis of national and international policy documents related to biodiversity and sustainability

Coding process

Coding was carried out as a form of qualitative content analysis. This began with the formation of the codebook that was used to guide the coding process, while allowing for emergent themes to develop and help shape the data that was constructed. The codebook was based on a combination of responding to key messages and themes (e.g., approach to justice) from chapter 2, as well as drawing upon existing conceptual frameworks (e.g., Life Frames) to guide the analysis. The 'codes and criteria' table below illustrates how the codes related to the key messages of the chapter. In terms of developing the codes to characterise the various policy instruments that were described in the documents, these were drawn from Böcher's (2012) literature-based typology of instruments; (i) informational, (ii) cooperative, (iii) regulatory and (iv) economic. Similarly, the coders outlined four types of governance structures; (i) State-funded, (ii) Market led, (iii) Civil society based and (iv) Education. On both of these codes we allowed for the possibility of mixed instruments and governance structures as it emerged that no documents rarely advocated one single approach. In terms of the coding itself, the majority of the codes entailed descriptive content as opposed to a pre-defined typology or data range. This descriptive content were either direct references from the data itself, or were summarised statements from the coders' own understandings. For example, in terms of coding for the definitions of instrumental, relational and intrinsic values, coders searched for both implicit references as well as explicit references in the data. Implicit references were discussions about the particular type of values where definitions were suggested indirectly or were implied, and so there was no direct reference to the specific value type. On the other hand, explicit references were made directly and clearly stated a definition to the value type.

To ensure quality control during the coding process, the three coders regularly discussed and communicated individual processes and methods for coding the documents. As a result, the data was constructed through an iterative process, whereby changes were made to the codebook as emerging themes developed. For example, on the theme of levels of participation, the three coders found that documents could be characterised on two levels in response to this inquiry: (1) participation in the context of how decision-making will be carried out via the document's proposed actions, and (2) participation in the context of who contributed to the production of the policy documents themselves.

Codes and criteria

Topic one: Policy document type / context

1. Title, year of publication, level [international, regional, national, subnational]
 - a. Actors participating in the process of making the document

2. Type of policy document

- a. Strategy / Vision
- b. Forming concrete policies
- c. Recommendation / Assessment
- d. Other

3. Nature of the policy document

- a. Law
- b. Policy instruments
- c. Policy targets
- d. Partnerships
- e. Mixed

4. Grand challenges

- a. GC 1
- b. GC 2
- c. GC 3
- d. GC 4
- e. N/A - applied when there was no clear reference to any of the GCs or when several of them were developed, in which case, details were provided.

5. Targeted policy topics

- a. TPT 1
- b. TPT 2
- c. TPT 3
- d. TPT 4

- e. N/A - applied when there was no clear reference to any of the GCs or when several of them were developed, in which case, details were provided.
- 6. Environmental conflicts referred to in the document
 - a. Details were provided when environmental conflicts were addressed.
- 7. Type of policy instruments discussed/respectively favoured
 - a. Informational (education/persuasion)
 - b. Cooperative (voluntary agreements)
 - c. Economic (market-based/price mechanisms)
 - d. Regulatory (command and control/legislations)
 - e. Other/multiple (add description)
- 8. State the specific policy instrument
- 9. If those instruments were mentioned:
 - a. What was their purpose?
 - b. How were they motivated? (ideological grounds, previously proven effective, theoretical, etc.)
 - c. What was the expected outcome?
- 10. What was the governance structure to support the policy instrument?
 - a. Type: State-funded, Market led, Civil society based, Education, Mixed
 - b. What are the motivations for this governance structure to be used?
 - c. Side effects (positive/negative) of using the structure?
 - d. How did the policy instrument/governance structure sit with local/cultural norms? (Key phrase, examples or overall impression).

Topic two: Knowledge system/worldviews

- 11. Level of involvement/participation suggested
- 12. Knowledge gaps identified?

13. Knowledge system used to support/frame the specific values focus

- a. Scientific/technical
- b. ILK
- c. Other non-Western
- d. Multiple/integrated

14. What HNR are expressed/implicit in worldview or philosophies? (An overall impression of the document).

- a. Biocentric - intrinsic value of organism/life valuable.
- b. Ecocentric - intrinsic value of species and ecosystems - importance of a systemic view rather than single things.
- c. Anthropocentric - human superiority or, other focus on human perspectives but not limited to a narrow and instrumental understanding of the relations between people and environments/nature (aesthetic dimensions, reliance on natural processes). Dependence and stewardship. Overlap with others.
- d. Pluricentric/non centric/dualistic/relational: focus on relationships between humans and other-than-humans. (Not one center but a network of relations).
- e. Other worldviews that appear in the paper (describe).

15. Monistic / Dualistic / Pluralistic approach

16. Value types (implicit or explicitly stated)

- a. i. Instrumental / ii. Relational / iii. Intrinsic
- b. Are there any discussions about concepts?
- c. Value indicators used: monetary, biophysical, socio-cultural.
- d. Method of aggregation (commensurability to a single scale) - used/discussion about strength/limitation.

17. Explicit efforts to form/change values

- a. Dynamic processes/social/socio-ecological factors?

18. Plural/multiple values obscured by either not mentioning them (obscured) or by focusing one type of value (slightly obscured) or by focusing on one type of value (slightly obscured). Plural/multiple values prioritised when explicit reference of their integration. (Description if implicit/Quote if explicit).
19. Role of institutions in guiding value formation or solicitation
20. Negative framings of values or ecosystem disservices
21. Map values/HNR on to the LVF
 - a. Living from
 - b. Living with
 - c. Living in
 - d. Living as
 - e. Combination

Topic three: General themes

22. Approach/frame on justice (environmental, procedural, intergenerational, redistributive, recognition, epistemic)
23. How are risk/uncertainty approached in relation to catastrophic events? Recognises/seeks to minimise/accepts and works with the risk.